

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CASE STUDY ON ENGLISH PROFICIENCY OF ESL STUDENTS BASED ON APPLICATION OF BLENDED LEARNING APPROACH

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Abstract

Blended learning which is a form of flipped learning is considered “new normal” “new styles combined with technology” in higher education. Thus, it has been developing as future trends and increasingly applied in teaching foreign languages today. Blended learning approach has become vital part of foreign language teaching and become a dominant one in higher education and teaching innovation. Therefore, this paper aims to analyze the progress of students’ academic English skills focused on subject areas of PEARSON STEAM content via implementing blended EFL courses that combined and designed on Internet platform Moodle LMS utilizing online and in-class instructional materials. The findings of the research were analyzed focusing on the students’ improvement both in academic English and linguistic skills through online (Moodle) and paper tasks (Apply skills). The students’ English proficiencies were assessed at the level of Intermediate to High-Intermediate by the Global Scale of English (GSE) which is aligned with the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR). The results were evaluated and described with the qualitative research methods.

Keywords: Academic English, E-learning system, Face-to Face Teaching, Blended model, Flipped learning Moodle Learning Management System, Pearson - STEAM content.

Introduction

Blended learning from a technological perspective, is a grouping of online learning tools that let students interact with the course material via an online learning management system while studying entirely from home (Nguyen Ngoc Vu, 2021). This is one of the most important approaches for ensuring quality education, particularly in providing numerous possibilities for lifelong learning, as specified in the fourth Sustainable Development Goal. The SDGs spotlight many businesses; nonetheless, it is evident that the education sector is just as vital as the other industries. The English language is regarded as important in the subject of education since it is widely recognized and used as a global communication medium (Ramalingam, 2022). Blended learning is becoming increasingly popular in language, foreign, and in-class courses. The effectiveness of learning English with a blended learning system, this approach is appropriate for students learning foreign languages whose age is still accessible and comfortable with the use of learning technology, internet tools as a means of learning foreign languages.

Furthermore, virtual learning application tools make it easier to teach English in the technological age (Husna Imro'athush Sholihah, 2021). According to Hassan there are three parts to blended learning: organizational, pedagogical, and technological components (Hassan, 2021). The components of technology include computers and network connectivity. E-learning policies, funding, training, and senior management support for the use of online learning are examples of organiza-

tional components. The way that teachers use technology and high-quality information in the classroom is characterized by pedagogical components.

BL offers numerous advantages, such as granting students access to computers and local and global information networks; fostering the development of teachers' roles as leaders and mentors to their students in terms of their expertise in computers and local and international information networks, as well as being producers rather than importers of knowledge; allowing learning groups to use collaborative software for multimedia, e-mail, virtual libraries, and all internet data; combining various opportunities for various schools and universities in a productive manner; and resolving the issue of long-term changes in the content of educational materials (Oweis, 2018).

Literature Review

Benjamin defined the flipped classroom model is a successful teaching strategy in which students participate in higher-order thinking exercises that promote teamwork in problem-solving, in-depth idea exploration, and the creation of real assessment tasks. Students are encouraged to participate actively in class discussions, which supports their demand for competence and autonomy. Diverse customized in-class activities are advised by proponents of the flipped classroom model, which allows teachers to work with a larger number of learners (Benjamin Aidoo, 2022).

It has also been demonstrated that blended learning can improve students' English competency while they are studying the language as a foreign language (EFL) or as a second language (ESL). According to studies of Sebastianus Menggo and others integrating

blended learning into English classes has the potential to improve students' language and non-linguistic proficiency (Sebastianus Menggo, 2022).

There are many sets of models of blended learning implementation (Lim, 2015). Station rotation model (SRM) is defined by Horn and Staker as an implementation that includes online learning inside a specific course or subject that the students would rotate on a set schedule or when the teacher assigns the students. Simplified, it's the process of assigning and completing assignments to students in a conventional classroom setting while incorporating technology and internet resources.

Bengi Birgili concluded that the shift from traditional educational techniques to non-traditional technology-based methods has been largely attributed to flipped learning. Students believe that the use of active learning pedagogy in the classroom is beneficial on their attitude, accomplishment, cognitive abilities, and soft skills since they assume greater responsibility for their own learning (Bengi Birgili, 2021). Similarly, Waheeb. S noted that blended learning has been shown to be an excellent tool for improving language proficiency, improving the English learning environment, and increasing students' willingness to learn the language, according to the current review of the literature (Waheeb S. Albiladi, 2019).

Study of Bakeer indicates the results that blended learning approach can help students to take responsibility for their own learning by making them autonomous and confident. In other words, they were motivated to learn English and believed that the blended learning method helped them to develop their learning and communication skills (Bakeer, 2018).

Furthermore, Nguyen Ngoc Vu conducted a study on Moodle that is a very useful tool for teaching and studying English. Using Moodle's writing features, teachers can effectively arrange lesson plans, create communication channels, and obtain student contact information through the comprehensive statistics report (Nguyen Ngoc Vu, 2021). Various kinds of language-learning resources can be found on the Moodle website. By simulating real-world environments, the images, audio, and video files can increase learners' motivation to learn English as a second language. (Jingwei, 2013).

Research results

The research was focused on the analysis of applying blended learning approach in higher education in Mandakh University. In order to achieve the research purpose, the objectives were followed to provide the research procedure systematically. Data were collected from on the basis of tests results on the Moodle, as result of online classes and in-class assignments performance.

As academic sources textbooks are among the most common and essential didactic tools in both face-

to-face and distance learning. We use the University Success Intermediate-High Intermediate Level. It is an academic skill series designed for English language learners who can read, write, and communicate orally. The authentic material of University Success weaved through all three strands permits rigorous skill development and wider application, which are essential for students to become confident and competent in a university setting (Carrie Seenburgh, 2018).

University Success's three-part framework includes focused and methodical skill development linked to learning outcomes, as well as rigorous academic content topics which are selected from science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics (STEAM), which are areas of mainstream academic study. The three-part structure gives for the greatest flexibility. Each unit's structure provides for flexibility, such as when using the FLIP Classroom Model (F-flexible learning environment), (L-learning culture change), (I-intentional content), or (P-professional educators). A flexible learning environment in a flipped model pertains not only to the physical learning spaces—i.e., small groups, pair work—but also to the teacher's freedom regarding which topic should be taught in the classroom and which outside (Suwarna Rani Subramaniam, 2016).

In Parts 1 and 2, students learn core reading and critical thinking abilities. Both Parts 1 and 2 conclude with a "Apply Your Skills" segment. These parts make excellent project or exercise-based unit assessments. Part 3 offers students a completely authentic academic experience allowing them to enhance and apply the abilities learned in Parts 1 and 2. With University Success, the teacher has the opportunity to use flipping approach. Both techniques provide students with access to instructional content both in and out of the classroom. (Pearson Education, 2018).

With flipping, students engage with content outside of the classroom and apply their newly acquired skills inside the classroom. For example, outside of class, they may complete reading exercises and comprehension questions. Back in class, with completed notes and exercises in hand, they're ready to engage in discussions and group activities. When selecting outside-of-class activity, consider offering tasks that students will most likely complete at varying rates. A more in-depth reading is an excellent example. When assigned a longer reading as homework, students have the option of reading it as many or as few times as they need. Everyone in the following class will have a similar basic comprehension of the material. (Pearson Education, 2018).

This chart shows one way to teach a unit using the FLIP approach.

Table 1

FLIP approach.

Part 1, 2	In Class	Flip
Introductory Video		✓
Warm –op questions	✓	
Skills 1 and 2		
Presentation (Explanation & examples)	✓	
Vocabulary preview	✓	
Warm-up exercises	✓	
Reading, writing and discussion or debating exercises		✓
Comprehension and collaboration exercises	✓	
Vocabulary check	✓	
Applied Exercises		✓

The Global Scale of English is a standardized, granular scale ranging from 10 to 90 that assesses English language competency. It complies with the Common European Framework of Reference. Unlike the CEFR, which describes performance in terms of broad levels, the Global Scale of English identifies what a student can do at each point on a more detailed scale—and within a CEFR level. The scale is intended to motivate students by exhibiting incremental improvements in their linguistic abilities. The Global Scale of English serves as the foundation for Pearson English course materials and assessments. The CEFR and the Global Scale of English both include a number of Can perform statements, or "learning objectives," for each of the four language skills, which describe what learners should be able to perform at various levels of ability. The learning objectives are written to reflect what a learner "Can Do" with language, regardless of the environment in which a language ability may be demonstrated. The GSE

Learning Objectives have been matched with the CEFR, and numerous new statements have been generated, assessed for difficulty, and calibrated to the scale (Pearson Education, 2018). University Success is in line with the Global Scale of English and the Common European Framework of Reference. It advances learners from CEFR B1 to B1+ (43-58 on the Global Scale of English). The Intermediate to High-Intermediate level prepares students for real-world academic environments through authentic content and careful integration of fundamental abilities. Each lesson leads students to a "Can Do" goal that aligns with the Global Scale of English and the Common European Framework "Can Do" statements (Pearson Education, 2018).

The research results were described according to the research objectives. The research was undertaken among 28 senior students, classified 22 females and the rests males, who are in the range of 20-25 years old.

Table 2

Demographics of Respondents

Demographics		28 participants
Age		18-25
Gender	Female	22
	Male	6
University Level		4 th -year

Each unit begins with is a short inspirational idea that captures the essence of the certain topics in the STEAM content, such as The Human experience, Money and Commerce, The science of Nature, Arts and Letters and Structural Science. Outcomes list the unit skills that help the students' academic and language knowledge, with the tie of the Global Scale of English. In the table 2 as below, 6 fundamental and 6 critical thinking skills in terms of reading, oral and writing strands in the context of Bioethics and Chemical Engineering were considered that how the students have obtained them. The learning procedures were coordinated

in E-Mandakh - In Class - Moodle LMS form which provides blended learning system. For instance, all seminar contexts were located in E-Mandakh e-learning system for pre-study case for students. Skill presentations were introduced through slide share and particular tasks were completed in the classroom. According to the blended approach students practice assignments such as introductory and concluding videos, reading, writing and discussion or debating exercises; and other applied exercises in distance.

Table 3.

Lists of learning skills				Code
Lists of skills				
Fundamental Skills <i>Unit: Bioethics</i>	Reading	Skill 1	Identifying cause and effect	Fundamental Reading Skill 1 (FRS 1)
		Skill 2	Examine examples	Fundamental Reading Skill 1 (FRS 2)
	Listening & Speaking	Skill 1	Identifying parts of a presentation	Fundamental Oral Skill 1 (FOS1)
		Skill 2	Planning for a presentation	Fundamental Oral Skill 2 (FOS 2)
	Writing	Skill 1	Understand the visual appearance of writing	Fundamental Writing Skill 1 (FWS 1)
		Skill 2	Proofread effectively	Fundamental Writing Skill 2 (FWS 2)
Critical thinking skills <i>Unit: Chemical Engineering</i>	Reading	Skill 1	Identify facts	Critical Thinking Reading Skill 1 (CTRS 1)
		Skill 2	Identify opinions	Critical Thinking Reading Skill 2 (CTRS 2)
	Listening & Speaking	Skill 1	Identify and express facts	Critical Thinking Oral Skill 1 (CTOS 1)
		Skill 2	Identify and express opinions	Critical Thinking Oral Skill 2 (CTOS 2)
	Writing	Skill 1	State an argument	Critical Thinking Writing Skill 1 (CTWS 1)
		Skill 2	Support an argument with example	Critical Thinking Writing Skill 2 (CTWS 2)

As the research paper aimed to analyze the progress of the academic skills of learners, the following table has demonstrated the criteria for language proficiency and the learner's target skill in GSE&CEFR columns. Learning results of our students are shown in the colored column out of 100 percent as locally. The learners' target scale is 43-58 by GSE and B1 & B1+.

Table 4.

Criteria for learning outcomes				
Academic skills	Criteria	GSE (43-58)	CEFR (B1 & B1+)	100 points
FRS 1	Recognize relationships of cause and effect in an academic text	52	B1+(51-58)	63.0
FRS 2	Identify examples to find supporting ideas	54	B1+(51-58)	76.0
FOS1	Use basic discourse markers to structure a short presentation	45	B1 (43-50)	52.0
FOS 2	Give a simple presentation about topic in a field	57	B1+ (51-58)	65.0
FWS 1	Practice taking notes when study a relevant topic	53	B1+ (51-58)	62.0
FWS 2	Write an essay based on common structure	46	B1 (43-50)	44.0
CTRS 1	Recognize differences between fact and opinion	47	B1 (43-50)	77.0
CTRS 2	Recognize key information among an extended text	57	B1+ (51-58)	59.0
CTOS 1	Use basic expressions and sentences to express attitudes	52	B1+ (51-58)	53.0
CTOS 2	Respond simple questions in a discussion.	50	B1 (43-50)	58.0
CTWS 1	Support a key idea with explanations and examples	55	B1+ (51-58)	53.0
CTWS 2	Support a main idea with examples and rationales	57	B1+ (51-58)	62.0

There was a calculation of GSE versus 100 points in the table 4 to illustrate how the learning outcome is aligned to GSE and CEFR. The figures in the last column are the result of the online assignments via Moodle learning management system.

Table 5.

GSE versus Students' learning outcome					
Skills	Existing outcomes (out of 100)	Estimation	GSE (43-58)	GSE vs Existing outcomes	CEFR
FRS 2	76.0	54*100/58=93 (GSE); 54*76/93=44.1	54	44.1	B1
CTRS 1	77.0	47*100/50=94 (GSE); 47*77/94=38.5	47	38.5	A2+
FOS 2	65.0	57*100/58=98.3 (GSE); 57*65/98.3=37.7	57	37.7	A2+
FRS 1	63.0	52*100/58=90 (GSE); 52*63/90= 36.4	52	36.4	A2+
FWS 1	62.0	53*100/58=91.4 (GSE); 53*62/91.4=36	53	36.0	A2+
CTWS 2	62.0	54*100/58=93 (GSE); 54*62/93=36	54	36.0	A2+
CTRS 2	59.0	57*100/58=98.3 (GSE); 57*59/98.3=34.2	57	34.2	A2
CTOS 1	53.0	52*100/58=90 (GSE); 52*53/90= 30.6	52	30.6	A2
CTWS 1	53.0	52*100/58=90 (GSE); 52*53/90= 30.6	52	30.6	A2
CTOS 2	58.0	50*100/50=100 (GSE); 50*58/100=29	50	29.0	A1
FOS1	52.0	45*100/50=90 (GSE); 45*52/90= 26	45	26.0	A1
FWS 2	44.0	46*100/50=92 (GSE); 46*44/92=22	46	22.0	A1

As seen there, only FRS 1 (Identifying cause and effect) met the target scale of the language proficiency of the learners, in the scale of 44.1 and B1. This result showed that our students have developed the fundamental skill of examining examples to improve their reading in the intermediate level, has not reached in higher intermediate level yet.

Thereon, the fundamental reading, oral and writing skills, namely, identifying cause and effect, planning for a presentation, understanding the visual appearance of writing, as coded FRS 1, FOS 2, FWS 1, were developed in the criteria of A2+, which are in the high beginning level. The critical thinking skills such as identifying facts, supporting an argument as abbreviated as CTRS 1 and CTWS 2 were equaled in 38.5 out of 47 and 36 out of 54 scales, which were accounted in A2+, in high beginning rate. As seen the result, students have been equipped with both of fundamental and

critical thinking skills in 4 language skills (reading, writing, speaking, listening) step by step, but haven't been reached their target scale yet. The critical thinking skills, those are identifying opinions, identifying and expressing facts and stating an argument, as known CTRS 2, CTOS 1 and CTWS 1 were rated at A2, still in the beginning level, which we need to focus in the further learning outcome. Identifying parts of a presentation, proofreading and identifying and expressing opinions in writing and oral communication tasks resulted poorly in 26, 22 and 29 respectively, those were leveled in A1 that is a need for more practice.

In order to review the learning outcomes, an inbound test was taken by all of the students at the beginning of the course and an outbound at the end of the term.

Figure 1. Inbound & Outbound test results

As shown in the figure 2, inbound result was 48.5% out of 100%, which occupied 24.25 according to the GSE and at the beginning level as A1 with CEFR. Outbound result was 72% out of 100%. It was equaled

to 41.7 and A2+ with GSE and CEFR respectively. The result has showed that there was 23.5 points improvement that moved from A1 to A2+ level. The improvement was kept through the progress achievements of

learning both in class and online. However the students' target scale has not been performed yet, that need to concentrate on developing the academic English skills.

Conclusion

In summary, the learning outcomes of the students haven't met the target objectives of English proficiency according to the GSE criteria. With this reason, there is a need to review the subject syllabus, learning environment, teaching methodology and learners' expectations to identify where a gap is, in order to see further academic growth. The findings indicate that we should focus on students' engagement to apply or practice those new skills not only in the classroom but also in the real-life situations. In terms of maintaining blended learning environment, technological, pedagogical and organizational components as learning facilities can be supported to reach the target objectives of English proficiency of the learners.

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